

Original software publication

EBLT — Blueprints testing library using fuzz testing

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ABSTRACT

Low-code and no-code paradigms are accessible, but lack mature testing methods. This gap needs to be addressed as such applications provide a way for stakeholders to interact with or define the requirements of applications in video games, digital twins, and simulations. Blueprints are an example of this paradigm, enabling a visual definition of functionality or requirements. We proposed an open-source tool that uses fuzz testing and applied it to Unreal Engine blueprints. Tests triggered by stakeholder changes are automatically generated, offering support for tuning parameters and optimizing testing time.

Code metadata

Current code version
Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version
Permanent link to Reproducible Capsule
Legal Code License
Code versioning system used
Software code languages, tools, and services used
Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies
If available Link to developer documentation/manual
Support email for questions

v1.0
<https://github.com/SoftwareImpacts/SIMPAC-2023-505>
MIT Licence
git
Python, C++, C#
Unreal Engine 5 (UE 5)
Installation and usage guide: <https://github.com/unibuc-cs/EBLT-Fuzzing-Software-Blueprints/blob/main/README.md>
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Body of the article (excluding metadata, tables, figures, references)

Low-code or no-code application development is a strategy in which applications are created by linking blocks of operations and data at a high level of granularity, mainly via a graphical interface. This approach offers several advantages: First, it enables faster prototype development, allowing multiple types of stakeholders to participate in the development, testing and evaluation process. This is possible because the visual linking of blocks is more comprehensible for people without programming skills. Secondly, the architectural specifications are more transparent for stakeholders, than technical documentation, which leads to improved product quality and easier maintenance. Involving non-technical stakeholders in the development of technical software artifacts has led to mixed results, but we believe that focusing on testing will improve the results [1]. Lastly, concealing low-level operations and legacy source code can shift the focus from minute details to high-level processes. However, to ensure the quality of this software development paradigm, testing must be an integral part of

the overall development process and should be as accessible as the low-code specifications themselves. Generally, automated testing is performed by a technical role, but in the low-code paradigm, this step should also be definable by the non-technical stakeholders (see Fig. 1).

The design and architecture of the software stemmed both from the authors' experience in video game development industry and from the requirements gathered from industrial partners — video game companies located in Bucharest, Romania.

Architecture

Blueprints are defined as low-code libraries of functionalities. Generally they are developed using drag-and-drop in the interface of the blueprints engine application, in our case the Unreal Engine. Blueprints are a set of functionalities that are compatible with the application and can be reused in other projects, or distributed through a marketplace. Our testing infrastructure relies on two major components also described in Fig. 2:

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Fig. 1. Example of how blueprints are defined and used in the Unreal Engine 5 tool. For each node, the inputs are shown on the left and the outputs on the right. The white connections between the arrows show the connections of the nodes, i.e., the concrete function flow. The other types of edges represent reading/writing data at the inputs or outputs of the nodes. (a) Member variables definition inside a blueprint, containing parameters for camera positioning. (b) Example of blueprint that adjust camera positioning based on jump action (c) blueprint establishing weather to suspend actor control by player.

Fig. 2. Description of the fuzzing-based test generation process. It should be noted that fuzzing can be replaced as a testing methodology with others based on the specific requirements of the application-under-test.

- Fuzzing process, our selected testing approach, which selects functionalities and inputs to be included in the test.
- Execution process, which selects an agent and executes the functionalities and inputs selected by the Fuzzer. Its output is then fed back into the fuzzer to improve the selection process.

To maximize future compatibility with other engines, we implemented a layer of abstractization between our library and the layouts and definitions of the blueprints.

The test cases are described using BDD (Behavior-Driven Development) methodology in order to provide the high level interface for the tester. Initial tests defined using the Gherkin notation use a user provided JSON file that provides values which will later be used in the test case. The fuzzer can create additional tests by tuning the parameters of the test. It is valuable to note that the agents that control the testing and tuning are separate from the application processes, in order to ensure portability.

Process

For academic purposes, we used Unreal Engine’s Hour of Code content to validate our solution. We designed a blueprint that makes an

in-game agent accomplish a series of objectives — collect objects, and reach a certain destination. These objectives are defined programmatically as artifacts similar to, but more complex than the ones described in Fig. 1 (b) and (c). The agent is an in-game character that a player controls. Given the multiple combinations of locations in the game, agent characteristics, and sequence of events, it is impossible to predict every possible permutation, and therefore test them. We listed in the JSON file all the values that functionality specific parameters may have during gameplay. Most values were not given nominally, instead an interval of values was used. Upon starting the testing process, the fuzzer initially chooses blindly test parameters to build a test case. Subsequent choices are made informed by previous test case results in order to maximize the identification of scenarios that determine failure.

Alternative to testing, the library also enables tuning of parameters. Instead of optimizing for discovery of permutations that end up in failure, using the tuning settings the tester can aim to discover the permutations that optimize scenario outcomes. For example the combination of starting point, speed, and size, which determines the fastest completion of the game. The results of both testing and tuning are displayed as seen in Fig. 3 and logged in a file, for further analysis.

Impact Overview

This library allows pursuing the following research question:

- **How can low-code artifacts, specifically blueprints, be included in the automatic testing practices of developers?**

Enabling testing of blueprints has had an impact in both academic and industrial contexts. Our tool addresses the issue of applying state-of-the-art testing methods to a fairly new software development paradigm [2]. As an example, we have applied fuzz testing, a testing paradigm that is gaining popularity, to the blueprints of a video game developed with the most popular game engine. As far as we know, this is the first tool to apply this testing method to blueprints, and provides the foundations to continue improvement in automatic testing

Fig. 3. Screenshot of the game running automated generated tests, with an overlay displaying the success or failure of each test, or tuning step.

of blueprints. We looked specifically at blueprints as an artifact to test, as it is a new paradigm and interest in its implementation is growing [3] (see Table 1).

Table 1
Bug distribution in four commercial games.

Games	L10	NSH	L12	LH01	Total
Crash	89	16	10	30	145 (10.75%)
Stuck	22	7	9	27	65 (4.82%)
Logical	379	25	22	62	488 (36.17%)
Balance	476	88	20	55	639 (47.37%)
Experience	476	88	20	55	639 (47.37%)
Total	973	138	63	175	1349 (100.00%)

From an industry perspective, this library is primarily aimed at developers of video game experiences. A development team at one of our industry partners used the prototype of our tool for 9 months. Most members of the team did not have the technical skills to write test code, as it consisted of 4 software engineers, 3 game designers, 7 animators, 5 technical artists, and 2 producers. However, one of the most remarkable results of applying our tool to real projects was the increase in “the percentage of components tested ... especially for features introduced by stakeholders other than software engineers” [4]. This result confirms our research goal, which is that the same stakeholders who design using blueprints can also contribute to testing their artifacts.

The source code has been published online and can easily be integrated according to the documentation by other studios using similar development engines. Further maintenance updates have been made available for the source code to ensure compatibility with the latest versions of the prerequisite software, specifically Unreal Engine, and license compliance.

The software described in this article is based on the results described in:

1. Păduraru Ciprian, Cristea Rareș, Ștefănescu Alin. Automatic fuzz testing and tuning tools for software blueprints. Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Software Technologies (ICSOFT'23), distinguished with Best Paper Award. SciTePress, pages 151–162. ISSN 2184–2833. doi: [10.5220/0012121900003538](https://doi.org/10.5220/0012121900003538)

Limitations and further developments

Currently, our library has been validated only on Unreal Engine as the blueprint creation platform. Porting this library to other game

engines requires minimal effort as it does not depend on a technology-specific implementation (such as .NET) and is a future work goal. The other major platform for video game development – Unity – also allows users to deploy their library developed in Python, ensuring portability and the potential coverage of a large number of game development projects. The methods used in this software can also be applied to other types of interactive experiences outside of video games. A valuable future perspective may come from the integration with symbolic/concolic execution, which will allow expanding state-of-the-art high-level methods to lower-level artifacts.

Conclusion

This paper presents EBLT - a tool for general low-code artifact testing with proven applications in blueprints for video game testing using Unreal Engine 5 and fuzz testing methodology. The proposed tool is suitable for optimizing test resources in large projects, leveraging state-of-the-art paradigms.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ciprian Păduraru: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation. **Rareș Cristea:** Validation, Investigation, Software, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Alin Ștefănescu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpa.2024.100674>.

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